

The journey of lung cancer patients through the health care system in Bulgaria: Insights from patient-reported outcomes

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Abstract

In recent years, there has been a growing body of literature on how digital technologies enhance patient engagement through patient-reported outcomes (PROs). The evaluation of PROs related to patients' experiences of diagnosis and treatment, as well as their interactions with health care professionals and the health care system, provides important insights into how digital solutions can improve patient experience and support higher-quality, patient-centered care and decision-making. We conducted an online survey using Referendo, a web-based platform for collecting patient-reported outcomes (PROs) and patient experience data. The main findings from the survey focus on the journey of lung cancer patients through the health care system in Bulgaria and assess various aspects of the patient experience, including the quality and effectiveness of medical and treatment services, as well as time to diagnosis, treatment, and drug safety. It also highlights the significance of communication and interaction with health care professionals, as well as the importance of social and psychological support for patients diagnosed with lung cancer. The results show that patients' feedback is important not only for clinical decision-making but also for resource and service allocation. Patients want to talk about their disease, their health, their psychological status, and their experience. Patients need to talk about the impact of the disease on their social life and working environment. In conclusion, PROs are valuable tools that can enhance decision-making and optimize the patient's journey through the health care system.

Keywords

digital solutions, lung cancer, patient journey, patient-reported outcomes

Introduction

Patient-reported outcomes (PROs) are considered a powerful tool in health care decision-making, especially in key therapeutic areas such as oncology. They help capture patients' perspectives on the whole patient journey, including diagnosis and treatment benefits as well as risks, particularly given that cancer and its therapies often lead to substantial symptoms, adverse effects, and impairments in daily functioning. This patient-derived information can then inform regulatory and health care decision-making by supporting assessments of the overall benefit–risk balance of treatments and gathering insights into the quality of life of patients (Bellino et al. 2024; Yamaguchi et al. 2025).

Understanding the patient journey through the health care system at a national level is essential for identifying gaps that could impact the time it takes to diagnose and initiate treatment. These delays can significantly affect therapeutic outcomes, particularly in fields such as oncology. In this context, adopting digital technologies can be beneficial for quickly gathering patient perspectives, identifying bottlenecks, reducing delays, and improving communication (Santos et al. 2026).

The current study aims to collect and analyze various aspects of lung cancer patients' interactions with the health care system in Bulgaria, including their experiences in diagnosis and treatment and the barriers, based on the digital web-based patient referendum platform Referendo.

Methods and materials

We conducted a 4-month prospective study among 1,150 unique patients with lung cancer from six towns with important oncology centers – Sofia, Plovdiv, Varna, Pazardzhik, Stara Zagora, and Bourgas. The survey aimed to collect and analyze patient-reported outcomes (PROs) regarding the health care services they receive. Specifically, with this report, we aimed to assess the following indicators—(1) lung cancer patient journey with possible gaps and solutions; (2) health behavior and satisfaction of patients with lung cancer, including critical thinking, personal responsibility, attitude toward others, and financial issues; and (3) interaction with health care professionals and mental health and attitude toward living with the disease. The survey was conducted through Referendo – a web-based patient referendum platform aiming to empower patients and their families by conveniently collecting patient-reported outcomes (PROs)—feedback, experiences, opinions, and ideas about important health issues. This platform seeks to assess the influence of Referendo on patient engagement and health outcomes.

This survey covered four domains with the following subtopics and inclusion criteria:

- **Demographic profile** of patients diagnosed with lung cancer, including data for age, ethnicity, mar-

ital status, and education, as they were recruited on a random basis.

- **Diagnostics and treatment:** with a focus on time living with the diagnosis, time to diagnosis from first symptoms, type of therapy, treatment duration, and adverse drug reactions.
- **Challenges and constraints:** financial difficulties affecting diagnosis and treatment, emotional impact of diagnosis, assessment of physical condition, social support, access to medical services, and transport.
- **Interaction with the health system and health care professionals:** satisfaction with communication, organization of work in the health facility and downtime, level of access to medical services and therapies, and feedback on delays.

Statistical analysis

To examine the relationships between the individual indicators, a cross-tabulation analysis (joint frequency distribution) was conducted. The results were also processed using descriptive statistics.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Medical University of Sofia (No. 3589/18.08.2025) before study initiation. Participation was voluntary, and all respondents provided informed consent before completing the survey. The survey was anonymous; no identifiable personal data was collected, and all responses were handled confidentially and used solely for research purposes.

Results

Demographic profile

A total of 1,150 unique participants entered the survey, and 1,140 (99%) completed the questionnaire. Seven hundred (61%) of the respondents were male, and 440 (39%) were female. Seventy-six percent of the patients were above the age of 60 (Table 1). Their feedback is considered statistically representative of all lung cancer patients in Bulgaria.

Among the participants, 242 (47.4%) felt confident that their feedback could be valuable to decision-makers and could help improve the pathways for lung cancer patients within the health care system.

Diagnostics and treatment

Most patients were diagnosed with lung cancer within 6 months before the survey began. Pulmonologists and general practitioners were the primary health care professionals who first referred these patients for lung cancer diagnosis. Twenty-eight patients reported living with the

Table 1. Demographic profile of the patients.

Indicator	Sofia	Plovdiv	Varna	Panagyurishte	Stara Zagora	Burgas
No of patients	327	156	201	201	90	165
Male	178 (54%)	93 (60%)	145 (72%)	101 (50%)	64 (71%)	119 (72%)
<44 y	11	0	1	1	0	2
44–59 y	29	22	27	14	11	23
60–69 y	102	41	60	57	31	47
>70 y	32	30	57	29	24	47
Female	149 (46%)	63 (40%)	56 (28%)	100 (50%)	26 (29%)	46 (28%)
<44 y	11	1	0	1	1	0
45–59 y	25	18	21	13	5	18
60–69 y	75	19	18	62	12	16
>70 y	30	25	17	24	8	12
Education						
High school	175	89	106	177	57	125
Bachelor's degree	78	13	29	15	7	17
Master's degree	70	15	13	0	5	0
Working status						
Retired	130	83	113	67	47	101
Not working at the time of the survey	96	25	30	42	18	16
Working	98	46	58	92	24	47

diagnosis for more than 5 years, of whom one patient was diagnosed 10 years ago. Computed tomography was the main diagnostic tool, used in 860 (76%) of the patients at the time of diagnosis. Eighty-six percent ($n = 974$) of the respondents had non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), from which around 30% were diagnosed at stage III and more than 50% at stage IV (Fig. 1).

Immediately after diagnosis, pharmacotherapy was prescribed for 857 patients (76%), with 223 of them also receiving radiotherapy. Two hundred three (18%) patients underwent surgical treatment.

Overall, pharmacotherapy was prescribed to 1,012 patients (89%). Among them, 356 were on immunotherapy; 272 were receiving combined chemotherapy and immu-

notherapy, and 263 were on chemotherapy. Pain management was considered for 220 patients (Fig. 2).

Treatment discontinuation was observed in 10% of the patients ($n = 113$). Among the main reasons reported were toxicity, progression of the disease, noncompliance (patients refused treatment), and contraindications for treatment.

Challenges and constraints

Most of the patients ($n = 1,099$) did not report any financial constraints that postponed or hindered access to diagnosis and treatment. One thousand one hundred three (97%) patients reported no issues accessing medical ser-

Figure 1. Diagnostic patterns of the lung cancer patients in the survey cohort.

Figure 2. Treatment patterns of the lung cancer patients in the surveyed cohort.

Table 2. Treatment patterns according to the stage of lung cancer.

Stage of LC	Chemotherapy	Immunotherapy	Combined chemo- and immunotherapy	Target therapy	Target + chemotherapy	Target and immunotherapy	Chemo-, target and immunotherapy
I stage	8	8	6	3	0	1	0
II stage	20	11	17	3	2	0	0
III stage	94	120	63	13	3	0	0
IV stage	112	162	144	74	7	1	2
Not aware about stage	22	54	44	1	0	0	0

vices related to the disease. Among those who experienced challenges, the most frequently reported reasons included engaging relatives, transportation issues, and difficulties in scheduling appointments for oncologist consultations.

Out of 300 respondents, 175 indicated that their physical and medical conditions had an impact on their financial well-being. Most patients surveyed ($n = 1,086$) reported having social support for daily activities, personal care, and assistance from family and friends. Additionally, 777 lung cancer patients noted that they spent several days involved in activities related to their disease. Overall, most patients rated their current physical and emotional well-being as very good compared to their condition at the time of diagnosis (Fig. 3).

Interaction with the health system and health care professionals

A total of 1,100 patients believed they had timely access to medical services. For those who experienced issues and delays, the primary reasons reported included difficulties in obtaining appointments with pulmonologists, insufficient information about their condition, challenges in organizing radiotherapy, the distance to hospitals, financial constraints, and issues related to diagnostics.

Out of the patients surveyed, 1,032 reported that they received adequate information about the therapy and its safety profile. However, nearly half of the patients ($n = 479$, or 42%) indicated that they either lacked information

Figure 3. Psycho-emotional and physical state at the time of diagnosis and during the survey.

or required more details about consultations and available social support groups (Fig. 5).

Oncologists were the most highly rated health care professionals during the diagnostic process, particularly in communication, followed by general practitioners and pulmonologists (Fig. 4).

Eighty percent of the patients showed very good satisfaction with their experience in the respective hospital during their treatment (Fig. 5).

certain combinations of values occur significantly more frequently than others.

A key feature of the observed data is the clustering of frequencies around central categories for certain indicators, indicating relative stability of the measured parameters. Statistically significant differences suggest that the observed variable relationships reflect genuine structural patterns rather than random variation.

4A. Patients' satisfaction with healthcare professionals during the diagnostic process

Total number of respondents 1133

4B. Patient's satisfaction with the communication with healthcare professionals during diagnostics and treatment

Total number of respondents 1133

Figure 4. Patients' satisfaction with the health care professionals during the diagnostic and treatment process.

Figure 5. Patients' satisfaction with the health care system.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis indicates that the analyzed variables exhibit different patterns of frequency distribution, including both symmetric and asymmetric structures. Cross-tabulation analysis reveals statistically significant relationships ($P < 0.0001$) among some of the indicators (i.e., gender and age and belief that the patient's voice can contribute to improvement in patient journey; age and stage of diagnosis; age and timely access) and shows that

Discussion

This study is the first of its kind in Bulgaria to collect patient-reported outcomes from oncology patients. It focuses on their satisfaction with treatment, medical services, and interactions with the health care system from the patients' perspective. The results from this survey prove that patients' feedback is important not only for clinical decision-making. It could be beneficial in terms of resource and service allocation.

The findings could complement other published studies in the region that assess access to medical services and the patient journey for women with breast cancer. These studies indicate that there is still a need for improvements in health policies within the Central and Eastern European (CEE) region to reduce disparities and inequalities in the availability of breast cancer health services (Dimitrova et al. 2020).

The current study outlines some important findings: (1) lung cancer is still diagnosed in the late stages of the

disease, stages III and IV, and most of the patients are above 60 years of age, and (2) some obstacles that could delay diagnosis and treatment include the distant location of the oncology hospital, financial issues, difficulties with scheduling appointments with health care professionals, and lack of access to medications.

These findings align with other studies. Petrov et al. examined the feasibility of implementing a national lung cancer screening program in the Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries. The study results indicated that screening rates remain low, particularly in the Balkan region. Key barriers to implementation include financial issues related to low-dose computed tomography (CT), a shortage of trained radiologists, a lack of political will, disagreement among health care professionals regarding the use of low-dose CT, and low levels of public awareness (Petrov et al. 2024). In a retrospective analysis of lung cancer patients, Dudov et al. identified a significant need to address the lack of lung cancer screening programs in Bulgaria and to ensure equal distribution of oncology centers at the national level (Dudov et al. 2025).

The time taken to diagnose symptoms and initiate treatment typically ranges from 1 to 3 months for most of those surveyed. This suggests good accessibility to both diagnostic services and treatment options, indicating a well-functioning health care system. Patients are likely able to receive timely diagnoses and appropriate care. The treatment approaches follow international guidelines, showing that clinical practice is aligned with established standards. This supports findings from previous national studies, which have reported similar levels of compliance not only in lung cancer but also across other oncology fields. Additionally, this level of alignment may contribute to improved patient outcomes, as adherence to evidence-based guidelines is associated with more effective and consistent care. It also supports better coordination between health care providers and helps ensure that patients receive standardized, high-quality treatment regardless of the institution (Karanyotova et al. 2023; Dudov et al. 2025; Arabadjiev et al. 2025; Petrova et al. 2026).

In a study published in 2025, Milushewa et al. analyze the problem of drug shortages in Bulgaria in terms of procedures and unmet needs. The authors' findings show that key therapeutic areas such as oncology, cardiovascular care, and intensive care were impacted by significant shortages of medicines for hospital use. Nevertheless, these medicines are included in a Specialized Electronic System for Tracking and Analysis of medicinal products listed in the Positive Drug List via a specific national tracking system (Ministry of Health of Bulgaria 2025); there is still a need to optimize the national strategies in terms of regulatory, economic, and market dynamics and adopt some EU good practices (Milushewa et al. 2025).

The study provides new insights into patient and health care professional interactions, which are crucial for advancing screening rates, personalized, patient-centered care, and improving clinical decision-making. Pulmonologists and general practitioners are the primary health

care professionals who initially refer patients for lung cancer testing. Therefore, awareness campaigns should focus on these professionals to increase understanding of lung cancer risk factors and promote early detection within society. The latter could also address the finding that many people still lack adequate information about these risk factors and the disease itself. To address this gap, it could be beneficial to establish more public awareness campaigns and develop digital solutions to provide the necessary information. The INSPIRE-Lung Study showed that social media and digital platforms could benefit society, including not only high-risk groups but also the public who are unaware of or lack access to lung screening (Carter-Bawa et al. 2023).

Most patients express satisfaction with their interactions within the health care system and their communication with health care professionals, particularly rating oncologists very highly. This positive feedback supports the adoption of the concept of shared decision-making, which is already recommended in the ESMO guidelines for early and locally advanced non-small cell lung cancer (Zer et al. 2025). Moreover, there are already published studies in Bulgaria among other health care professionals (oncohematologists and endocrinologists) that show that, although this concept is still not well known in Bulgaria, health care professionals apply it in an unstructured manner (Petrova et al. 2025).

Finally, the survey results indicate that Referendo could be effectively used to collect patient-reported outcomes and real-world data, particularly in assessing patients' experiences and pathways with chronic conditions such as lung cancer. The results suggest that Referendo may be a useful digital channel for collecting PROs and patient experience data; in this survey, participants used the platform to share perspectives on their disease and interactions with the health care system. A regular collection of patient-reported outcomes through the Referendo platform could help continuously improve the Bulgarian oncology system. By using real-world data in health policies, it becomes possible to close the gap between having treatments available and making the system work efficiently.

Conclusion

Collecting patient-reported outcomes (PROs) and real-world data (RWD) consistently is essential, especially in understanding patient journeys through the health care system. PROs and RWD serve as powerful tools for improving decision-making and optimizing patient experiences. Additionally, digital tools can effectively engage patients and facilitate the sharing of their perspectives and voices.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Secure server on Referendo platform, hosted by B-eye

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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